

User Education in Academic Libraries

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Abstract

The ultimate goal of librarian and library is to educate users in locating their information needs at the right place, in the right time to right user to save their time in encouraging and motivating their reading habits. User is the most important component in the library or in information system and they are the last links or the recipient of the information in communication cycle. This paper focus in user education in academic libraries with special reference to school libraries in understanding the library users, how they interact with the systems, facilities and service available in the library in which they are engaged and their patterns of retrieving their required information. User education is broader term than bibliographic instruction. Education is the long life process, there is no end. As far as library activities are concerns, the users are illiterates. They need some sort of user education on how to use library resources, facilities and services. To know how to use and what the service available is etc, they must be assists and guide in the right path. As a result through user education and library orientation, it facilitates users in locating and accessing their various types of information needs and requirement.

Introduction

User is the most important component in library or in information system and they are the last links or the recipient of the information in the communication cycle. Availability and access to right information to the right users at the right time can build on to new directions to higher studies for instance; research and development. Our librarians and information managers though appear committed the doctrine of service provided to users, to facilitate their retrieval for documents. Library instruction, also called “bibliographic instruction”, “user education” and “library orientation. Therefore, the paper aims to focus in user education in academic libraries. User education is broader term than bibliographic instruction.

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Objectives

Some specific objectives have been laid down to understand the user education in academic libraries. They are:

1. To define users, user education and academic libraries.
2. To categories the types of users
3. Identify the needs of the user.
4. Analyse the needs for user education.
5. Identify the users' characteristics.
6. Library user education programme.

Definitions

A. Users

Any person who uses the resources and services of a library, not necessarily a registered borrower is known as user.

B. User Education

Various definitions of user education coined by information scientist are presented below:

- 1) All the activities involved in teaching users how to make the best possible use of library resources, services, and facilities' including formal and informal instruction delivered by a librarian or other staff member one-on one or in a group is known as user education. It also includes online tutorials, audiovisual materials, and printed guides and pathfinders (**Reitz 2004**)
- 2) User education is concerned with the library whole information and communication process and one art of this involves the total user interaction of user with the library (Nancy, 1984) require".
- 3) Shahi said "It is a process of activities involved in making the users of the library conscious about tremendous value of information in day-to-day life to develop interest among the users to seek information as and when they.

C. Academic Library

An Academic Library has been defined as: "a library which is associated or attached with any educational institution to support its educational programmes". Academic library is an integral part of formal education system which provides time bound education from primary school level to university level. An academic library works as a base for teaching, learning, research etc. We can categorize academic libraries into three categories:

1. School Library
2. College Library
3. University Library

a) Definition of School Library

A library associated or connected with a school and used by the students, teachers and staffs of that school is called a School Library.

b) Objectives of School Library

A school library has the following objectives

1. To supports all educational programmes of the school;
2. To cultivates reading habits in school children;
3. To develops their interest to use the library for their overall development
4. To inculcates the habit of seeking information of additional sources other than text books.
5. To develops self-learning skills of students;
6. To nurtures good moral values and principles in the children
7. To cultivates a feeling of respect and love for nation and its culture in the students.
8. To helps teachers to improve their teaching expertise;

9. To provides healthy material for recreational and entertainment purpose to students, teachers and staff members.
10. To keeps the teachers and management informed with the latest updates in education sector.

c) Functions of School Library

To achieve the above said objectives a school library performs the following functions.

1. It provides suitable documents and information helpful in educational programmes and extra-curricular activities of the school.
2. It makes available text books and other additional reading material for all subjects as per the requirement of teachers and students;
3. It procures handy documents, illustrated picture books with bold and large fonts colour to create the interest of children in reading.
4. It procures latest teaching learning material in the form of books, CD, audio-visuals etc. to improve the teaching skills of teachers. It procures latest teaching learning material in the form of books, CD, audio-visuals etc. to improve the teaching skills of teachers.
5. It keeps reference books, dictionaries, year books, directories, encyclopedias, travel books etc. so that students and teachers can get help of these other than the text books.
6. It also keeps some books on easy self learning like how to use computer, to develop the learning skills of students.
7. It makes available biographies, autobiographies of freedom fighters and other national and international personalities to develop respect and love for nation and humanity.
8. It procures magazines like Tinkle Digest, Readers Digest etc., different newspapers, and other light reading material like fiction books, general knowledge books, poetry books, short animated films, documentaries, etc. for healthy recreation and entertainment purpose of students, teachers and school staff.
9. It provides books of simple and meaningful stories of classics, animals and birds to give moral values and ethics to children.
10. It also procures bulletins, journals etc. on different subjects and various aspects of education to keep the teachers and school management updated in their respective areas (Gupta, 2002).

Categories Of Users

Library users are of one type which is called 'USER' but due to their demands and requirements of information it can be categories the types of libraries. In a public library the users are mainly children, student's, housewives, farmers, retired persons, literates and even also researches. In an academic library the users are students, teachers and researchers, whereas as special groups of users of whom the library is intended. The main categories of users can be categories into four groups, such as; potential user, expected user, actual user and beneficiary user.

1. Potential Users are one who needs specific information and know what he/she is needed which can be provided by specific services. e. g. query of a particular book for reference or issuing for his/her study purpose.
2. Expected Users are one who is known to have the intention of using certain information services and library facilities. e. g. I) Browsing and accessing online resources available in the library. ii) Users' online searching i.e. OPAC (Online Public Access Catalogue).
3. Actual Users are one who has actually used of an information service regardless of whether he derived advantages from it or not. e. g. availing the entire library services particularly circulation services such as issue, return and renewal of documents.
4. Beneficiary Users are one who derives measurable advantages from information services. e. g. Potential users, expected users and actual users are the main example of beneficiary.

User groups may be divided in a number of ways. They can be divided as administratively into internal and external users. Internal users are the users which are the institute or school membership whereas; external users are the library users other than the institute or school members, coming from outside but avail the library facilities. Another type of classification of user community on the basis of library service they make use of, is as following:

1. **General readers:** This type of user group, for example associated with public libraries, generally use light lending materials.
2. **Subject readers:** This type of user concentrates their use of library materials on subject field they are working or specializing or research area.
3. **Special readers:** The users placed in this group are those with special needs, the result of disabilities of one kind or another physical or mental disability may be distinguished.
4. **Non-readers users:** These are made up of sub-groups who make use of library materials, but not reading materials. A user coming into the library just to borrow a video or audiocassette is the best example of non-reading user.
5. **On the basis of various type of services:** Dr. S. R. Ranganathan has grouped user community on the basis of various types of services enunciated by him. They are the freshman, ordinary inquirer, specialist inquirer and general reader. Here the freshman is the new member of the library, ordinary inquirer is ordinary reader and specialist inquirer is one who specializes in narrow field where as general readers are the associated groups. In order to satisfy these groups, Ranganathan has suggested four types of services such as; initiation or orientation, ready reference service, long range reference and general help to general readers respectively.
6. **Non-users:** In case of public library, there are certain people who because of geographically or other environmental problems could not become members of libraries in their vicinity and make use of the library resources (**Kumar, 2009**).

Nature Of Information Need

Information needs is a complex process. 'Information' is put to different uses and 'Need' is satisfied by having access to the identified information in a particular package and form, and at a suitable time (Wilson 1981). Users are in constant need of information and the average user spends an estimated twenty percent of his time searching for it. Perhaps some of the most valuable deductions from the user studies have been about the nature of information need in a composite concept of different types of requirements and approaches to information. It is generally accepted that there are four different types of information requirements or approach. They are; Current approach, Everyday approach, Exhaustive approach, and Catching up or brushing up approach or browsing approach.

a) Current Approach

The current approach arises from the need to keep up, to know what other workers in the field are doing (or about to do). Surveys of both scientists and technologists have shown that the most important source of such information is a fairly small core of primary periodicals, systematically scanned. Of great importance too are personal contacts with colleagues, with visitors, and at conferences. Secondary sources such as abstracts and indexes, if used at all are regarded as guides to the primary sources.

b) Everyday Approach

The everyday approach arises in the course of daily work, regularly and frequently, usually in the form of a need for some specific piece of information vital for further progress. Unlike information needed in the current approach, it can usually be found in a number of places, and to the user the source is of little concern provided it is reliable. Almost invariably the one nearest to hand is chosen, and the emphasis is on finding what wanted as soon as possible is. This approach is the one most frequently used by scientists and technologists.

c) Exhaustive Approach

The exhaustive approach usually arises when work begins on a new investigation, and involves a check through all the relevant information on a given subject. It is called for less frequently than the current or every day approaches, but is vitally important, and often urgent.

d) Catching up or Brushing up Approach or Browsing Approach

The browsing approach by definition unplanned and certainly inefficient, is nevertheless a fruitful path to information, definitely part of the scientific and technological communication system, and could well be added to Voigt's three approaches. Hence, deliberately or otherwise, but without any specific topic in mind, workers seek information outside their predefined areas of interest, the aim (or result) being to extend the boundaries of that interest. Surveys have shown that printed sources play a major 'Triggering' role in stimulating new ideas and interests (Nagaraju, 2009).

Identify The Needs of Users

Use" is the key purpose and 'User' is the key and dynamic component of any library and information system. Customer oriented approach; design and evaluation are the founding pillars of any enterprise. As such use and user studies including non-use and non-user studies are required to be carried out as long as library and information systems are required and existing. Here, the user includes 'non-user' and user includes potential user, non-user, under-privileged, un-served, underserved and deprived users. A non-user could be an involuntary non-user who do not have a library to use or voluntary (willful) non-user. A voluntary non-user is one who has access to a library and lives in information rich society and yet suffers from information malnutrition (Sridhar, 1994)

The users come to the library with various information needs, but with minimum possible time. But it is not so easy for the librarian to fulfill all the needs of the users since users may not express their need exactly due to various complex psychological characters. It is the duty of librarians to ascertain information needs by putting a series of questions. It is also to be remembered that the user needs are ever changing and complex one (Mews, 1972).

Services To the Users

Services to the users can be provided as follows:

1. Search assistance by using OPAC or in the stack;
2. Inter Library Loan;
3. Media services, such as: internet access and audiovisual;
4. Reference service;
5. New document request for requisition and the same notified when acquired;
6. Borrow/Return/Renew (Circulation);
7. Photocopying and Translation;
8. Orientation and library tour.

User's Characteristics

Systematic study of user community will reveal the various characteristics of users seeking information. This will give necessary base guidelines to librarians to serve various types of users groups. The user's characteristics enunciated by Lehman are:

1. Personality level.
2. Variability level.
3. Capacity level.
4. Satisfaction level.
5. Functional reading level.
6. Visual level.

Library User Education Programme

User education programme is the main objectives of the library for the best and maximum used of library target to the users. It can be studied under three main sub-topics.

a) Library Orientation

It is an introduction to library building, online catalogue (i.e. OPAC) and some basic reference materials. The orientation aims at:

1. Motivation for searching and using the information,
2. Creating awareness about available information resources,
3. Exposing them to various organisational tools of the library.

The different methods of orientations are as follows:

1. **Lecture method:** the formal / informal.
2. **Advertising:** (Paper, Journal, Posters, Pamphlets) although limited to a particular small geographical area, but in case of online it requires very wide advertisement through papers, journals, etc.
3. **The Workshop:** About the CD-ROM, online services (then gives hands on practice-workshop).
4. **Brochures:** It is brought out by each and every industry. It may contain history, use benefits, comparison purchases, addresses in brochures and leaves.
5. Newsletters.
6. Demonstration method.
7. Book exhibition.
8. Display of new arrivals.
9. Mass media/ audiovisual.

b) Library Instructions

It teaches the users, how to use the indexes bibliographic tools, abstracts and other reference materials. This method often gives instructions to the researchers in their field to get specific information resources. The aim of library instruction is to provide specific instructions for using and understand specific information system, information sources and tools (**Mishra & Mahapatra 2013**).

c) Bibliographic Instructions

Normally, it is difficult to use the bibliographic tools because of their organizational pattern. Thus, these instructions aim at exposing to the users to bibliographical tools, providing guidance's to understand the features of these tools and their nature of subject coverage. The tremendous increase in the volume of publications, the resulting complexity of libraries and the methods by which literature are organized and disseminated, necessitate the user education. Besides that, the rapid changes in teaching methods and the resulting trend towards a wider use of multi-media learning resources ranging from the press cutting to slide tapes package and multiple kit too. Such format has added new dimensions to the learning processes in all types of institutions. Hence, necessary bibliographic instructions have to be provided by the librarian to help the users to use those resources properly and get the benefit out of that (**Kumar, 2009**).

Conclusion

Library is a trinity of staff, resources or documents and users. Among them 'User' is the key and dynamic component of any library and information system. The thirst for information 'Need' is satisfied by having access to the identified information in a particular package and form, and at a suitable time. This is the impact of user education in the library, because it motivates for searching and using the information, creating awareness about available information resources, and exposing them to various organisational tools of the library. Therefore, user education plays an important role in academic library.

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